

Kinetic Study of Hydrolysis of Salicylanil Spectrophotometrically*

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The kinetics of hydrolysis of the Schiff bases, salicylanil (HL) have been investigated in 40% (v/v) ethanol-water medium in the pH range 4-13 at 25° and $\mu \approx 0.1$ mol dm⁻³. A rate profile diagram of pH vs rate constant exhibits rate minimum in the zone of pH range 7.83-10.3 and attains a plateau at pH >11.5. Hydrolyses of the Schiff base in acidic, neutral and basic media have been discussed and suitable reaction mechanisms suggested.

THE kinetic study of formation and hydrolysis of imines has received considerable attention in recent years owing to the transformation of C=O to C=N and vice versa in biochemical processes¹⁻⁴. Quantitative assessment of the catalytic effect of hydrogen ions, hydroxyl ions and various metal ions on hydrolysis of Schiff bases have been reported by several workers⁴⁻⁸. The present paper describes the kinetic study of hydrolysis of salicylanil in presence of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions.

Experimental

The Schiff base was prepared⁹ as follows. A mixture of salicylaldehyde and aniline was stirred gently on a water-bath. Globules of water appeared on the oily layer. The mixture was then placed in ice-water and stirred well. The resulting yellow solid was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 51° (Found: C, 79.1; H, 5.58; N, 7.11. Calcd. for: C, 79.18; H, 5.5; N, 7.10%); ν_{\max} (KBr; Perkin-Elmer) 3 080 (CH), 1 620 (C=N), 1 380, 1 190 (C=O) and 1 280 cm⁻¹ (OH bending). The pH measurements were made on a Elico LI-120 digital pH meter.

Kinetic measurements: Hydrolysis of Schiff base was studied in 40% (v/v) ethanol-water medium at 25° and $\mu \approx 0.1$ mol dm⁻³ (sodium perchlorate). Concentrations of the Schiff base was varied in the range $1-4 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm⁻³. Rate measurements were made in the pH range 4-13. Acetate, phosphate, borate and carbonate buffers were used in the pH range 4-5.6, 5.8-8.0, 8.2-8.8 and 9.2-10.8 respectively. Sodium hydroxide solution was used in the range 0.004-0.1 mol dm⁻³. In a typical kinetic run, a solution of sodium perchlorate, absolute ethanol and requisite amount buffer solution were allowed to equilibrate in a thermostat (25±0.1°). The reaction was initiated by adding a known volume of stock solution of Schiff base in

ethanol which was also maintained at the same temperature. After mixing, the reaction mixture was immediately transferred to one of the quartz cells and the decrease of absorbance of the Schiff base with time was followed against a reagent blank at 370 nm (pH < 9) and 420 nm (pH > 9). A Elico ULTRA-SPEC CL 54 spectrophotometer was used. Plots of $\ln(A_t - A_\infty)$ against time were straight lines and pseudo-first order rate constants calculated from the slopes of such plots.

Equilibrium constants: The protonation/deprotonation equilibria of the Schiff base (HL) may be represented as

The determination of pK_1 was attempted by glass electrode pH measurement by titrating Schiff base of known concentration against 0.01M HCl. According to equation (1),

$$pH = pK_1 + \log \frac{[HL]}{[H_2L^+]} \quad (3)$$

where [HL] is the concentration of Schiff base and [H₂L⁺] that of protonated Schiff base (The latter was calculated from the amount of titrant added and pH of the solution, as pH was solely dependent on the amount of titrant which remained unreacted. Thus from pH measurement the volume of titrant that failed to react was obtained and in effect the volume of titrant actually combined was calculated. [HL] was obtained from the amount of Schiff base which was originally present and the concentration of Schiff base which was converted to H₂L⁺). pK_1 was found to be 4.32 in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 25° and $\mu \approx 0.1$ mol dm⁻³. pK_1 of salicylanil has been determined by Lane and Kandathi¹⁰ at 25° in 50% dioxane-water (v/v)

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medium by conventional potentiometric titration. Dudek and Dudek¹¹ reported that Schiff base exists in keto-enol tautomeric equilibrium in ethanol-water medium. The presence of such equilibrium in ethanol-water medium is also expected to increase pK_1 of the Schiff base. Thus our finding of $pK_1 = 4.32$ is reasonably justified.

Schiff base anion exhibits an absorption maximum at 420 nm. pK_2 has been calculated spectrophotometrically⁷; $pK_2 = 10.49$ in 40% ethanol-water (v/v) medium at 25° and $\mu = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

Results and Discussion

Rate constants at various pH values are given in the Table 1. A rate profile diagram of pH vs rate constant at 25° and $\mu \approx 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, exhibits the rate minimum at $\text{pH} > 7.83$ and $\text{pH} < 10.3$ and attains a plateau at $\text{pH} > 11.5$ (Fig. 1).

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANT DATA FOR HYDROLYSIS OF SALICYLANIL

Ethanol-Water=40% (v/v), Temp.=25°, $\mu \approx 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

pH	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	pH	$k \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
4.04	84.15	9.47	—
4.49	19.54	9.82	—
4.82	8.00	10.80	5.95
5.25	4.03	10.76	7.20
5.81	1.14	11.50	7.79
6.21	0.94	11.92	9.42
7.00	0.22	12.21	9.78
7.83	0.18	12.54	9.50
8.25	—	12.91	10.53
8.76	—		

Fig. 1. Plots of k vs pH hydrolysis of salicylanil; temp.=25°, $\mu \approx 0.1 \text{ M}$.

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration: Rate constant varies linearly with hydrogen ion concentration in the pH range 4.49–7.83 (Fig. 2). However the value for pH 4.04 does not fall on the line ($pK_1 = 4.32$). This behaviour may be reconciled to the fact that imine is not appreciably protonated at $\text{pH} < 4.49$ and suggests that the acid-catalysis involves only the conversion of Schiff base to its conjugate acid in a rapid pre-equilibrium followed by slow attack of water⁸.

Effect of hydroxyl ion concentration: Rate constant was found to be independent of hydroxyl ion concentration (Table 2).

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF HYDROXYL ION CONCENTRATION ON RATE CONSTANT FOR HYDROLYSIS OF SALICYLANIL

Ethanol-Water=40% (v/v), Temp.=25°, $\mu \approx 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

$[\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	k $\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$[\text{OH}^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	k $\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
0.004	7.79	0.06	10.22
0.006	9.43	0.08	9.77
0.01	9.42	0.09	10.51
0.02	9.78	0.10	10.53
0.04	9.50		

Rate limiting pathways: In the pH range 4–13, the Schiff base may be assumed to undergo hydrolysis via four rate limiting pathways⁷: (i) acid-catalysed path involving addition of water to the imine linkage of protonated imine, H_2L^+ (k_1), (ii) a path involving addition of OH^- to the imine carbon atom of the protonated imine, H_2L^+ (k_2), (iii) spontaneous path involving addition of water to the imine linkage of neutral imine, HL (k_3), and (iv) a path involving addition of water to the Schiff base anion, L^- (k_4).

The overall rate of hydrolysis will be

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] + k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] [\text{OH}^-] + k_3 [\text{HL}] + k_4 [\text{L}^-] \quad (4)$$

Hydrolysis of Schiff base in mild acidic and neutral range of pH: In the pH range 4.49–7.83, equation (4) reduces to

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] + k_2 [\text{H}_2\text{L}^+] [\text{OH}^-] + k_3 [\text{HL}]$$

$$k = \frac{k_1}{K_1} [\text{H}^+] + \frac{k_2}{K_1} K_w + k_3 \quad (5)$$

A plot of k vs $[\text{H}^+]$ is a straight line (Fig. 2) with a slope of k_1/K_1 from which k_1 , the velocity constant for addition of water to the protonated Schiff base, is calculated ($k_1 = 29.41 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Since the intercept of the plot is zero k_2 and k_3 are zero, i.e. attack of hydroxyl ion on protonated Schiff base and spontaneous addition of water to neutral Schiff base may not be present.

Since no general catalysis (Table 3) was observed it may be assumed to be specific acid-catalysis. H_2L^+ is formed relatively faster in pre-equilibrium step and the rate-limiting step of the hydrolysis

Fig. 2. Plots of k vs $[H^+]$, temp. = 25° , $\mu \approx 0.1 M$; (●) $pH = 4.04$.

TABLE 3—GENERAL ACID-BASE CATALYSIS FOR HYDROLYSIS OF SALICYLANIL

Ethanol - Water = 40% (v/v), Temp. = 25° , $\mu \approx 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

(i) Acetate buffer ($pH = 4.41$)

$[HA] + [A^-]$ mol dm^{-3}	0.05	0.1	0.15	0.20	0.25
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	21.65	21.5	21.46	21.51	21.49

(ii) Phosphate buffer ($pH = 8.31$)

$[H_2PO_4^-] + [HPO_4^{2-}]$ mol dm^{-3}	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	0.69	0.66	0.60	0.63	0.54

(iii) Carbonate buffer ($pH = 10.52$)

$[HCO_3^-] + [CO_3^{2-}]$ mol dm^{-3}	0.008	0.016	0.024	0.032	0.04
$k (\times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1})$	8.89	9.21	8.86	9.11	8.85

reaction is the addition of water to the protonated Schiff base. This is further supported by the fact that at high $[H^+]$, i.e. $pH \approx pK_1$, velocity increases less rapidly than $[H^+]$ (Fig. 2)¹³. This is further confirmed as the proton transfer takes place to nitrogen atom¹³ of the imine linkage. Thus it is expected that the hydrolysis rate of (HL) increases as pH of the medium is lowered due to increase in the protonated Schiff base concentration in the same direction. In a slow step, the carbinolamine intermediate is formed and this is suggested to be the rate-limiting step followed by its decomposition to amine and aldehyde at a fast rate⁸ (Chart 1).

Hydrolysis in basic medium : In the basic range ($pH > 9.82$) the rate constant initially increase with increase in pH and reaches a limiting value at $pH > 11.5$. At this stage Schiff base may be assumed to be exclusively in anionic form (L^-) as $pK_2 = 10.49$. Hence the limiting rate constant can justifiably attributed to the reaction of Schiff base anion with water (k_4)⁷. The average value of the rate constant

Chart 1

at $pH > 11.5$ is taken as k_4 ($9.895 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). As the rate constant initially increases with the increase in pH ($pH > 9.82$) and then reaches a limiting value at $pH > 11.5$, therefore the complex formed can be assumed to be 'Arrhenius complex'. When the catalyst is present in excess 'Arrhenius complex' leads to 'specific hydroxyl ion catalysis' at low hydroxyl ion concentration and the rate reaches a limiting value at high hydroxyl ion concentration¹⁴. Since in the present case, at low hydroxyl ion concentration ($pH \approx 10$) the rate increases with hydroxyl ion concentration and may be assumed to be specific hydroxyl ion catalysis as no general catalysis was observed in this region (Table 3) and at high hydroxyl ion concentration it reaches a limiting value. This is indicative of the fact that the addition of water to Schiff base anion may be taken as slow and rate-determining step¹⁴. Thus carbinolamine is formed at a slow rate followed by its decomposition to aldehyde and amine a fast rate⁶ (Chart 2). Comparatively lower value of k_4 with respect k_1 may be due to the slowness of OH^- attack on the imine carbon atom under the effect of the high electron donor character of the ionised *ortho*-hydroxy group.

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References

1. A. V. WILLI, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, **39**, 1193; E. H. CORDES and W. P. JENCKS *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 826, 832; 1963, **85**, 2843; *Biochemistry*, 1962, **1**, 773; R. L. REEVES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 3332; R. L. REEVES and W. F. SMITH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 724; W. P. JENCKS, *Prog. Phys. Org. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 63; K. KOEHLER, W. A. SANDSTORM and E. H. CORDES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, **86**, 2413.
2. M. T. A. BEHME and E. H. CORDES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **87**, 260.
3. R. L. REEVES, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1965, **30**, 3129.
4. L. DOAMARAL, W. A. SANDSTORM and E. H. CORDES, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2225.
5. A. C. DASH and R. K. NANDA, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 6944.
6. A. C. DASH, B. DASH and S. PRAHARAJ, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 2063.
7. A. C. DASH, B. DASH and P. K. MOHAPATRA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1983, 1503.
8. F. A. ADAM, M. T. EL-HATY and S. A. EL-GYAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 37.
9. L. SCHISCHKOW, *Ann. Chem.*, 1857, **104**, 373.
10. T. J. LANE and A. J. KANDATHIL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 3782.
11. G. O. DUDEK and E. P. DUDEK, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 2406.
12. R. P. BELL, "Acid-Base Catalysis", Oxford University Press, New York, 1941, p. 126.
13. "Comprehensive Chemical Kinetics", eds. C. H. BAMFORD and C. F. H. TIEFFER, Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1977, Vol. 8, p. 34.
14. K. J. LAIDLER, "Chemical Kinetics", 2nd ed., Tata McGraw-Hill, New Delhi, 1978, p. 459-63.